

Synthesis and Studies of Some Naphthaleins*

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A number of naphthaleins obtained by condensation of phenols with naphthalic anhydride are described. The constitution of dyes has been studied and the Visible, UV and IR spectra have been presented and discussed. The absorption maxima of dyes are comparable with those of phthaleins.

Two analogues of phthalein dyes from naphthalic anhydride, phenolnaphthalein (phenolphthalein analogue) and naphthafluorescein (fluorescein analogue) are described in literature by Jaubert¹ and Terrisse². The yields described by them, however, are poor and the reactions far from smooth.

In the present communication, the authors have described the condensation of naphthalic anhydride with various aromatic hydroxy compounds in presence of a few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄. The dyes were obtained in yields ranging from 50–55%.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected. The absorption maxima (UV and Visible) have been recorded using Model DU Beckman Spectrophotometer in absolute ethanol (neutral and alkaline media) and IR were obtained from KBr on a Perkin Elmer infraord.

The phenols (II) (phenol, resorcinol, catechol, quinol, phloroglucinol and pyrogallol) have been taken in slight excess of molecular proportion than the anhydride (I). Concentrated H₂SO₄ has been used as condensing agent throughout and each dye, when tested, is found free from sulphur.

Resorcinolnaphthalein (naphthafluorescein) (IIIa ; R₁ = R₂ = R₄ = R₅ = R₇ = R₈ = H; R₃ = R₆ = OH) : Resorcinolnaphthalein was obtained by heating an intimate mixture of naphthalic anhydride (3.0 g) and resorcinol (3.8 g) with a few drops (4–6) of concentrated sulphuric acid at 180°–190° for 5 hr. The condensed mass was washed with water, dried, and extracted with 2% aqueous sodium hydroxide; the dye was precipitated from the pinkish red (green fluorescent) filtrate by gradual addition of dilute HCl with constant stirring. The dye was purified by repeated crystallisation from rectified spirit (yield 2.8 g).

The dye (brown powder) dissolves in ethanol producing a yellowish orange colour and light green fluorescence, which are intensified in colour and fluorescence on addition of alkali.

* The authors have adopted the nomenclature, for these dyes, as naphthaleins, for the sake of uniformity.

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TABLE I
Preparation and properties of naphthaleins (III) G.F. = Green fluorescence

Dyes	Condensation		Appearance	Colour in absolute ethanol+1 drop of 2% NaOH	EtOH		EtOH-NaOH		Analysis			
	Temp. °C	Duration hr			m.p. °C	λ _{max} (mμ)	λ _{max} (mμ)	λ _{max} (mμ)	pH	Calcd. % C	Calcd. % H	Found % C
Phenolnaphthalein (IV)*	135-45	9	190-92	light brown	reddish-pink	—	540	10.4	78.26	4.35	78.06	4.31
Resorcinolnaphthalein (IIIa)	180-90	5	> 300	brown	pinkish-red (G.F.)	480	510	9.8	75.39 (M wt, 382)	3.66	75.25 (M wt, 376)	3.89
Catecholnaphthalein (IIIb)	170-80	3	265-66	brown	pink red	495	510	9.9	75.39	3.66	75.23	3.86
Quinolnaphthalein (IIIc)	170-80	2.30	225-26	black	yellow-red	—	460	8.9	75.39	3.66	75.19	3.83
Phloroglucinolnaphthalein (III d)	200-15	0.30	> 300	yellow brown	light red	440	450 & 480	9.2	69.56	3.38	69.32	3.52
Pyrogallolnaphthalein (IIIe)	170-80	2	275 decomp.	brownish yellow	brownish yellow	490	390	9.0	69.56	3.38	69.33	3.40
Diacetylfresoreinolnaphthalein (III f)	130-40	4	150	light brown	pale yellow	330	330	8.2	72.03 (Acetyl, 18.45)	3.86	72.10 (Acetyl, 18.40)	3.99
Tetrabromoresorcinolnaphthalein (III g)	Room temp.	Over-night	200	red	pink (G.F.)	540	530	9.2	Br, 45.81	Br, 45.81	Br, 45.84	

* Excess phenol, after condensation, was removed by steam distillation.

The preparation of rest of the dyes, given in Table 1, has been carried out in identical manner as already described (yield 50–55%).

Chromatography of dye (IV): On Test paper—Whatman No. 1, *n*-butanol-ammonia was allowed to run for 13 hr (descending) to give a single pink spot of the dye (R_f , 0.94) showing purity of the compound.

Acetylation of dye (IIIa): The dye (0.5 g), acetic anhydride (10 ml) and fused sodium acetate (1.5 g) were refluxed at 130°–140° for 4 hr to give light brown microcrystalline compound (0.4 g) (from acetone), which is soluble in ethanol, acetone and acetic acid.

Bromination of dye (IIIa): The dye (0.6 g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute ethanol and 1 ml of bromine (excess) was added to it gradually with constant shaking. The contents left overnight at room temperature gave brick red tetrabromo compound (III g) (0.5 g) from acetone. It dissolved in ethanol producing pink red colour with green fluorescence, which were intensified on addition of alkali.

Caustic potash fusion of dye (IIIa): The dye (1.0 g) and a paste of KOH pellets (9.0 g) were taken in a platinum crucible and heated on a sand bath at 300°–320° for 3 hr till the pink colour of the dye faded completely. The contents were dissolved in 50 ml of distilled water and filtered; the filtrate on acidification with dilute HCl at low temperature gave a light yellow residue (A) which was reobtained on concentration of the filtrate. The filtrate was extracted with ether, and on evaporation of excess solvent a brown residue (B) was obtained.

Residue (A) washed well water, was found to be acidic in nature; on sublimation it gave white flakes of naphthalic acid (V) confirmed by m.p. and mixed m.p. (274°). Residue (B) was identified as resorcinol (VI) as it responded to ferric chloride, ammoniacal silver nitrate and Fehling's solution test. It was further confirmed by m.p. and mixed m.p. determination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The condensation of naphthalic anhydride (I) with phenols (II) takes place in an identical manner to true phthaleins (phenolphthalein, fluorescein etc.). The two analogues of phthalein dyes (phenolphthalein and naphthaflorescein) from naphthalic anhydride reported in literature by Jaubert and Terrisse were found to be in poor yield, however, in the present work yields were found to vary from 50–55%. The purity of the dye (IV) has been confirmed by paper chromatography. The structure has been confirmed by chemical and i.r. studies (3500 cm^{-1} , –OH and 1770 cm^{-1} , α , β -unsaturated δ -lactonic $>C=O$) Potassium hydroxide fusion of the dye (IIIa) produced naphthalic acid (V) and resorcinol (VI). The diacetyl derivative (III f) and tetrabromo derivative (III g) support the presence of resorcinol moiety in the dye (IIIa). The compounds (IIIa–IIIg) possess δ -lactone (1775 cm^{-1}). The peak at 3500 cm^{-1} (OH) in (IIIa) is found to be absent in (III f) and new peaks at 1200 and 1125 cm^{-1} (phenolic acetate) appear.

- (II) $R_1-R_5 = H \text{ or } OH$
 (IV) $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_9 = R_{10} = H; R_3 = R_8 = OH$
 (IIIa) $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = H; R_3 = R_6 = OH$
 (IIIb) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = H; R_4 = R_5 = OH$
 (IIIc) $R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = R_6 = R_8 = H; R_2 = R_7 = OH$
 (IIIId) $R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = R_7 = H; R_1 = R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = OH$
 (IIIe) $R_1 = R_2 = R_7 = R_8 = H; R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = R_6 = OH$
 (IIIIf) $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = H; R_3 = R_6 = OCOCH_3$
 (IIIg) $R_1 = R_8 = H; R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = R_7 = Br; R_3 = R_6 = OH.$

The absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of naphthalene derivatives have been found to be in good agreement with those of known true phthalic anhydrides prepared in similar manner (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Absorption maxima (m μ) of known phthaleins

Dyes	λ max		
	EtOH	EtOH—NaOH	pH
Phenolphthalein	—	550	10.8
Fluorescein	480	500	9.8
Eosin	530	530	9.9

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